

When identities get in the way!

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Abstract

The text addresses a critical assessment of Pedro Gómez García's article, "The illusions of "identity". Ethnicity as a pseudo-concept", based on other criteria on the role of cultural identities in the processes of preservation of the sense of belonging/difference among different human groups and on another theoretical approach to this topic.

Key words: ethnicity, "race", cultural identity, ethnic processes.

Resumen

El texto aborda una valoración crítica del artículo de Pedro Gómez García, «Las ilusiones de la "identidad". La etnia como pseudoconcepto», a partir de otros criterios sobre el papel de las identidades culturales en los procesos de preservación del sentido de pertenencia/diferencia entre diversos grupos humanos y de otro enfoque teórico sobre el presente tema.

Palabras clave: etnia, «raza», identidad cultural, procesos étnicos.

*Culture is the profound exercise
of identity.*

Julio Cortázar

Just as there is a wide literature specialized in supporting and enhancing the significance and actuality of the diversity of cultural expressions as a reference to identify and know identities in their multiple scopes, there has also been written to try to reduce to zero the notion of identity as a resource of human subjectivity that marks the senses of belonging/difference in individuals, families, groups, localities, regions or nations.

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One of many texts that has had a wide printed and digital dissemination is the article by Pedro Gómez García,² I refer to "The illusions of "identity". Ethnicity as a pseudo-concept". Let us see what this author proposes and how he puts forward his points of view. At the beginning of his argument, he starts with the deconstruction of the term when he identifies identity as "a confused idea". With an open mocking derision, he refers to it:

It is one of the words that has made the greatest fortune in recent decades, in the discourse of the social and human sciences, in the rhetoric of politicians and in the beliefs of people who have looked at it as in a narcissistic mirror: identity. Everyone is looking for it and believes they have found it; thinks they have lost it and can recover it. But, above all, people believe in the existence of identity, an identity of their own as opposed to other identities. It is the basis of rights, claims or grievances, the alleged legitimacy of aspirations, privileges, coercion, and violence exercised.³

As is evident, he tries to reify an idea that manifests the notion of belonging/difference and that transcends the "discourse of the social and human sciences" and reaches "the rhetoric of politicians and the beliefs of the people", which is the center of his interest, to reduce to zero, not only the current Spanish politicians (a localist vision that he addresses later), but also those who, supported by their sense of belonging, claim rights (migrants, for example, who are also human beings).

In this way, he restricts the notion of identity "to a restricted range of qualifiers, such as racial identity, genetic identity, ethnic identity, cultural identity, popular identity, national identity", and for this purpose he tries to approach a definition that can be dismantled for his claim when he refers that:

[The] "identity", apart from referring to the quality of the identical (that which is said to be the same as something else with which it is compared), alludes to "the fact of a person or thing being the same as that which is supposed or sought"; or in mathematics, the "equality that is always verified, whatever the value of the variable". Thus, identity can mean the permanence of the characteristics of oneself in relation to oneself (we suppose at different moments in time); or the exact similarity of the characteristics of one in relation to those of another (at different times or in different spaces). In the first case, one's identity is what constitutes one as

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³ All references cited are from the unpaginated digital version in Gómez García, Pedro. «Las ilusiones de la "identidad". La etnia como pseudoconcepto», in www.ugr.es/~pwlac/G14_12Pedro_Gomez_Garcia.html (Accessed March 5, 2018, 07:28 AM).

opposed to others, that is, what others do not share; in the second, it is what one and another or others have in common, that is, what they all share. This semantic ambivalence has slanted with all inertia towards the first meaning; although, being generally predicated of collectives, it preserves some of the sense of what is shared but emphasizing what is shared by one set as opposed to all the other sets, which supposedly do not share it.

Since the author fails to understand the dynamic and changing content in time-space of identity in human subjectivity; that is, *selfhood*, he qualifies it "as if it were an immutable, absolute and eternal essence". Similarly, otherness he reduces it "to a few differences with respect to the other," *without specifying what is the other?*

However, he contradicts himself when in the attempt to reduce the notion of identity to an illusion; that is, to a falsehood, he points out:

The concrete identity consists of the similar and the different. Especially when differences are usually more changeable than similarities. In the idea of identity there are aspects, ultimately individual and singular, aspects common to more than one group and *universal aspects*⁴ or common to all groups of the same species.

When in-depth studies are carried out based on field work such as ethnographic atlases, for example, it is found that both the similar and the different can and do change; this makes it possible to establish on a cartographic level the differences of the similar in the same territory or in different time periods. In the *Ethnographic Atlas of Cuba: Traditional Popular Culture*,⁵ a culinary expression such as the production and consumption of cassava in the Island during the second half of the 20th century is manifested in all provinces, but it is relatively scarce in the western half (from Pinar del Río to Ciego de Ávila) where the consumption of cassava is common through other ways of elaboration (salcochada/salted, fried, in sweets...) and profuse in the eastern half (from Camagüey to Guantánamo). However, in two census surveys of the colonial period (1827 and 1846) the situation was different until the current trend was achieved. The above serves to confirm the processes of change in cultural diversity at the provincial, regional, and national levels.

In his critique of the notion of identity as an immutable essence, he states:

⁴ On the alleged "universal" aspects see Jesús Guanche. «Diversidad cultural e identidad cultural: un binomio interactivo», en *Boletín. Por el desarrollo de la comunidad y la cultura*, Centro de intercambio y referencia iniciativa comunitaria (CIERIC), no. 3, La Habana, octubre 2017:4-8.

⁵ See *Atlas etnográfico de Cuba: cultura popular tradicional*, Havana, 2000 (CD version, Spanish and English).

In a universe in which even "elementary particles are often unstable",⁶ the concept of "identity" cannot but be problematic. And concrete identity on any plane, physical, biological, and anthropological, the product of a temporal evolution, is always a synchronic abstraction, the result of past differentiations and subject to further differentiations. The pretension of intrinsic and everlasting essentiality (sometimes disguised in historicist garb) is nothing more than an ignorant or self-interested, mendacious illusion, necessarily lacking in correspondence with the real characteristics of what is identified. It makes no sense to conceive of a substantial identity, when there are only multiple sets of elements that form syntheses, stably organized, whose being depends on interactions. Identity hypostases are only given their apparent solidity in thought by dark emotions, aroused by false ideas, and by real or imaginary interests that believe they find a firm foundation in the reification of the presumed identity that they themselves sponsor.

But the notion of identity approached from the dialectic in the sense of historical materialism is a much more complex and richer process than its placement in an essentialist and immutable box; therefore, he infers (this is his prejudice) that: "The "identity" approach generally presupposes an essentialist epistemology: that things are what they are, and that each thing is constituted by a determined set of fixed characteristics". And so, it reduces and encloses it:

The identitaria lens fixes the picture, takes the inevitably provisional for definitive, the temporal for eternal, the contingent for necessary. It interprets a result in which chance intervenes as the effect of a deterministic law. He does not grasp either where it comes from or where it goes, that which seems to him "identical" or identifying. He ignores that it always comes from something different and goes to something different, in incessant interchange with others.

This serves him as an argument to then attack the notion of ethnic identity and consequently ethnicity and the concept of ethnicity, which by the way he also uses in a very restricted and obsolete sense. Without alluding to certain authors, he points out:

It is highly likely that the anthropologists of "identity" have strayed from the scientific path, by placing the level of description in a few sensitive, symbolic, emblematic, "identity" traits, which have a markedly arbitrary, ideological, apparent, deceptive character with respect to the really existing sociocultural reality. It is ironic that, after having rightly criticized the

⁶ He refers to the work of Ilya Prigogine. ¿Tan solo una ilusión? Una exploración del caos al orden. (just an illusion? An exploration from chaos to order). Barcelona, Tusquets, 1983: 155.

"community" as an object of ethnological study, they have drifted towards that vaporous and volatile object that they have agreed to call "identity".

Thus, without specifying, he accuses those who have strayed from the path of science of devoting themselves to the volatility that he pretends to reduce to zero. That humans renounce to be what they are in diverse orders: personal, family, group, and others, especially, in defense of a shared sameness, with respect to those who pretend at present to flatten, like this author, the senses of belonging and become faithful subordinates of the global dominion of mentalities and of the world,⁷ since to globalize a way of being and doing, identities obviously get in the way.

He then, with both successes and slips, addresses the issue of "race as a biological pseudo-identity", a highly topical issue, especially in countries that still have the stigma of racism and racial discrimination rampant and that, rooted in the old notion of "race", persist in using the term as an identity resource.⁸ According to his unrenounceable Eurocentrism, he points out that:

Today it is not fashionable to speak of "race", at least to refer to one's own, although it is fashionable to allude to that of others: they call race to the gypsies, the blacks, the North Africans...; not so much to the countrymen, let us not go to look like Nazis. But there is no lack of those who persist in claiming racial prototypes, with their anthropometric measurements, highlighting the cephalic index, the blood group, and even very recent data on some gene frequencies. Such foolishness, if I were to contrast their pretensions, would inevitably lead me to the conclusion that any racial profile is comparable to any other and that the ancestors of any "race" can be traced back to the very origins of *Homo sapiens*. This constitutes an incontestable scientific truth.

He acknowledges the persistence of the term, due to the lack of adequate scientific dissemination, in ordinary language and in the mass media. After analyzing the scope and limitations of the budding physical anthropology, he rightly concludes that: "since the mid-seventies [of the 20th century], the concept of "race" has been expelled from physical and biological anthropology, because it is neither a scientific concept nor does it explain anything".

⁷ See Ignacio Ramonet. *El imperio de la vigilancia* (Havana, 2016) an excellent example of how the U.S. neoliberal globalization operates through the Web to appropriate mentalities and impose ways of life worldwide, in the behavioral order and especially as a business of transnational corporations.

⁸ See Paul C. Taylor. «El desriz de Malcolm y los colores de Danto; o cuatro peticiones lógicas relativas a la raza, la belleza y...» in *Criterios, revista internacional de teoría de la literatura y las artes, estética y culturología*, no. 35, Havana, 2003:50-59.

He criticizes the sources that persist in identifying supposed "races" in human beings and concludes that:

The most logical thing is to proclaim the abolition of the concept, as others have done, and to teach that what was under that word was something else, for whose knowledge it hinders. And the most accurate thing to do is to say unequivocally that [...] in our species there are no races. [...] There are no human races, just as the sun does not revolve around the earth, no matter how much it may seem so to us. It is necessary to explain it in another way: The appearance of races is produced by the movement of culture.

However, to exemplify the comparative studies in this regard, he falls back into the Eurocentric racist trap of identifying "the four great trunks: Caucasoid, Negroid, Mongoloid, Australoid", a construct limited to skin color whose studies reveal contradictory results: "According to morphological criteria, Mongoloids and Caucasoids form a group, and Negroids and Australoids form a different group. But according to immunogenetic criteria, Caucasoids and Negroids are similar on the one hand, and Australoids and Mongoloids on the other". The above allows blurring the fallacy of "racial identity", very much in vogue in U.S. social sectors still identified as "colored" and their followers in Latin America and the Caribbean as if it were a specific form of social and individual consciousness, unfortunately marked by the indelible imprint of racism. In this sense, he values that:

The development of population genetics has long ago ended up dissolving the idea of race, already abandoned by physical anthropology. Currently, what is studied is 1) the human genome, common to the entire species *Homo sapiens*, and 2) the diversity or genetic polymorphisms of the species, distributed among the different populations, measurable in terms of statistical profiles, variable over time.

In this way, it can establish a valid set of regularities, as a summary, which blur the false notion of "race":

- All human beings belong to a single and unique species, originating in Africa, expanded in the Old World 70,000 years ago, and in the New World 40,000 years ago.
- All population genetic differences are relatively recent, the result of adaptations to ecosystemic and climatic conditions; of spontaneous genetic drift and recombination; and of interbreeding between populations. There have never been "pure breeds". [...]

- It is not possible to draw clear genetic boundaries between one human population and another.
- The dominant genetic characteristics in a population are not transmitted as a compact whole, but as loose, recombinable traits that can be passed from one population to another. [...]
- All the genetic variability of human individuals belongs to the richness of the human genome, specific to the species. An individual from one population may share more genetic traits with individuals from other populations than with individuals from its own. Intra-population genetic variability reaches 85% of the traits, while the variability between one population and another only reaches 15%.

In this direction he overcomes the contradiction of the supposed four trunks according to skin color, but at the same time he takes a deep leap backwards when he reflects:

Well, if this happens with the "genetic identity", which is determined and closed for everyone from the formation of the zygote, what to think of the "ethnic identity", given that the traits attributed to it evolve much more rapidly and that they can even be modified throughout the individual's life? [and wonders]. Perhaps today ethnism is nothing more than a new face of racism.

This point of view, also conceptually limited about the notion of *ethnicity*, allows him to address "Ethnicity as a (bio)cultural pseudo-identity". In a crude and very unscientific way he refers:

In the theoretical market of the social sciences there is a growing offer for everyone to acquire their "ethnic identity", "cultural identity", "national identity", sometimes tailor-made. Reams for research and the obtaining of subsidies. Unredeemed causes for the ideological, political, and social mobilization of any indigenous people. The ethnological alchemy of these lustrums does not cease to distill elixirs of identity that, above all, the nationalist parties administer to the credulity of their followers. Each "people" tends to invest itself with a unique and privileged identity that makes it feel like a "chosen people", destined to arrogance, either because it exercises it, or because from its prostration it aspires to it.

It is obvious how those he describes as "indigenous"⁹ have sinned by being mobilized in social networks in order not to be swallowed by assimilationist policies under the banner of bringing civilization or moving towards "modernity". Nor does he differentiate between chauvinist nationalism and nationalism oriented towards self-determination, all very much in tune with the political situation in Spain and the struggles between the Popular Party (PP) and the Spanish Socialist Workers Party (PSOE).

With his contemptuous look over his shoulder, he says: "As people do not know very well what an ethnic group is, and even less that abstraction of "ethnicity", such words occupy the vacuum of concept and reality, like the alibi of a historical being endowed with its own personality, pre-existing before modern times and perhaps eternal essence, soul of the people, predestined people". This gives him the opportunity to enlighten the ignorant and he approaches "The invention of "ethnicity"" with a conceptual basis that is also obsolete and false.

He approaches the definition of the concept, according to him, as follows:

Etymologically the word ethnicity means nothing more than race or people. The dictionary of the Royal Spanish Academy says that it is a "human community defined by racial, linguistic, cultural affinities, etc.". In anthropology, the term "ethnicity" was at first nothing more than a euphemism, introduced to replace the word "tribe", which designates societies with a political organization that has not attained the form of a state, and whose organizational principles are based fundamentally on kinship.

In this sense it gives a very Eurocentric review of definitions limited to the other groups where the classifiers or the definers of the concept are usually excluded. Such as:

Ethnicity (sometimes confused with tribe) qualifies the largest traditional unit of species consciousness, at the meeting point of the biological, the social and the cultural: linguistic and religious community, relative territorial unity, mythical-historical tradition (bilateral descent from a real or imaginary ancestor), common type of organization of space. However, it may happen that several of the above-mentioned characteristics are missing.¹⁰

⁹ It is no coincidence that he uses the same colonial term used centuries ago by the Grand Admiral. See Jesús Guanche. "El estigma del discurso colonial," in *Perfiles de la cultura cubana*, no 21, January-June 2017, http://www.perfiles.cult.cu/inicio_c.php?numero=21

¹⁰ See André Akoun, *L'anthropologie*. Paris, Marabout, 1974: 169-170.

Ethnicity is a determined and collective reading of specific physical-cultural traits and a moment that makes possible the communication of a collective or social aggregate, especially within a larger one.¹¹

The above serves as a very shifting and fragile basis to subject to criticism three theoretical positions that he identifies as *essentialist*, *objectivist*, and *subjectivist*. In the first case, *essentialism* substantiates the notion of ethnicity "as a whole of fundamentally static constitutive notes, permanent over time, as if they instituted true temporality, outside history, immune to becoming", but does not allude to any author; in the second, he refers to the way in which Professor Isidoro Moreno approaches ethnicity in terms of sociocultural *objectivity*, who considers that ethnicity "exists when a human group possesses a set of economic and/or institutional and/or cultural characteristics that mark significant differences, both objective and subjective, with respect to other ethnic groups",¹² although he considers that the problem of how to categorize this characterization, how to establish the mark of the differences that are taken as significant, remains. The answer depends on the specific studies to be carried out and on their adequate theoretical formulation that facilitates interpretative certainty.

The third case relies on the social *subjectivity* of the members of a group and that of its neighbors; that is, at the level of people's consciousness and feelings. Thus refers the point of view of Elías Zamora: "The term ethnic group refers to the set of individuals who share a culture, some of whose traits are used as diacritical signs of belonging and ascription, and whose members feel united through a historically generated consciousness of singularity".¹³ The foregoing gives him grounds to try to shred the hard core of ethnic identity: *the consciousness of belonging to one's community*.

With this intention he considers that: "It is not admissible that superstition that sees the feeling as if it were an original, genuine and primordial datum; on the contrary, it is always something derived from endoculturation and learning". Precisely because it is derived from endoculturation, it is conditioned by objective and subjective factors of parents or tutors, which in turn influences learning processes. At the end of this part, he concludes with a philanthropic proposal: "Let us develop the consciousness and feeling of belonging to the

¹¹ See Jesús Azcona, "Etnia", in Ángel Aguirre Baztán (coord.) *Diccionario temático de antropología*. Barcelona, Boixareu, 1993: 257.

¹² See Isidoro Moreno. "Identidades y rituales. Estudio introductorio", in Joan Prat (and others), *Antropología de los pueblos de España*. Madrid, Taurus, 1991:611.

¹³ See Elías Zamora. "Grupo étnico", in Ángel Aguirre Baztán (coord.), *Diccionario temático de antropología*. Barcelona, Boixareu, 1993: 347.

human species, and we will all be one ethnic group!" Which also negates the remarkably diverse processes of human adaptation to the environment and the uneven development that injures most of the world's population.

When addressing "The incoherent components of ethnicity/ethnicity" he also subjects to criticism the work of Breton,¹⁴ who establishes two definitions of the constituent components of ethnicity, one circumscribed to the mother tongue and a broader one involving "a complex of common characters —anthropological, linguistic, political-historical, etc.— whose association constitutes a system of its own, an essentially cultural structure: a culture. [...] a community united by a particular culture".¹⁵ Thus, Gómez believes:

[...] that there is no validly generalizable concept of ethnicity, that is, applicable in all cases where it is empirically affirmed that one exists, whether by ethnologists, politicians, or the members of such a presumed entity. And here it is not a matter of noting the profuse use and abuse of this idea, but of analyzing whether its content corresponds to something consistent.

Obviously, Gómez did not access other more elaborate and forceful theoretical proposals on ethnicity based on diverse situations of human groups worldwide. One of them is that of the Russian scholar Yulian Bromlei (1921-1990), who for decades had valued ethnicity as a complex, changing process common to all mankind.

This author starts from a synthetic definition more comprehensive than those referred to above and relies on the Greek root: *ethnos* (ἔθνος, people), as "a stable group of people historically constituted in a given territory that possesses common cultural particularities, with a certain level of stability (including language and mentality), as well as awareness of its unity and its difference from other groups (self-awareness) fixed by self-designation (ethnonym)".¹⁶

Thus, the definition includes the stability of the group, the historical factors in relation to a territory, which can be for sedentary or itinerant conglomerates, the specific role of culture, such as language and mentality, together with the consciousness of unity and the difference with respect to others, identified with the ethnonym or autonym.

¹⁴ See Breton, Ronald J. L. *Las etnias*. Barcelona, Oikos-Tau, 1983.

¹⁵ *Ibidem*: 12.

¹⁶ Yulián Bromlei. «Etnos y sus tipos principales», in *Etnografía teórica*, Moscú, 1986: 6-38.

As they are changing processes in time-space, there is a set of main features that identify this type of human grouping. Those inherent to the individual/group subjective, which have greater stability, such as language (vernacular or mother tongue), self-consciousness (common ethnonym), idiosyncrasy (particular character), culture (knowledge /doings and their social relations) and endogamy (marriages within the group); those inherent to the spatial-temporality of the group, which have greater mutability, such as territory (influence on the notion of homeland and its standardization through the State), the mode of economic production (main characteristics of the relations of production) and state membership or formation (nation, part of one or several); and those inherent to the physical-biological aspect of people (their genetic variations).

But human groups are overly complex and can be categorized hierarchically, for example, according to their demographic size. He uses the generic category of *ethnikos* to encompass all members of an ethnos or ethnicity regardless of their permanent or temporary residence in a territory, such as the Han Chinese inside and outside China;¹⁷ the *Ethno-Social Organization* (ESO) to delimit the majority part of the ethnos or ethnicity linked to a state or government; and *transitional ethnic groups* characterized by their dual ethnic self-consciousness. These groups are specific to countries of emigration, such as: first- and second-generation emigrants assimilated by the host country's ethnos; emigrants who do not lose all ties with their ethnos of origin nor become fully integrated into the host country's ethnos; and ethnic border areas.

At the same time, given the level of complexity, they can be hierarchized according to their historical-cultural characteristics. Firstly, *meta-ethnic communities* can be identified, which include remarkably diverse peoples, such as *ethno-linguistic* (Anglo-Saxons), *ethno-cultural* (Latin Americans), *ethno-religious* (Catholics) and *ethno-political* (capitalists). Secondly, the *ethnos* or *ethnicities* themselves, either by their stage of socioeconomic development: *tribes* or *groups of tribes* (pre-class communities), *nationalities* (pre-capitalist formations) and *nations* (capitalist and socialist formations); or by their historical formation or ethnogenesis: *archaeogenetic* (formation of early class societies) and *neogenetic* (from capitalism onwards).

Third, *ethnographic* or *ethno-regional groups*, representatives of the part of a larger ethnos or ethnicity that retains differences from the main group in its ethnic territory (way of life, religion, dialect, folk culture); fourth, *ethnic groups*,

¹⁷ See globally Lynn Pan (General Editor). *The Encyclopedia of the Chinese Overseas*, Cambridge, Massachusetts, 1999.

representatives of the part of a larger ethnos or ethnicity that resides in another territory inhabited by one or several larger ethnos that constitute an *Ethno-Social Organization* (ESO), such as the Kurds who inhabit the territories of four states: Turkey, Iraq, Iran and Syria, together with a small enclave in Armenia; and fifthly, *ethnic minorities*, ethnos or ethnicity whose entirety or almost entirety live in their historically inhabited territory together with one or more quantitatively larger ethnos within one or several (ESO).¹⁸

But since the peoples of the world have had, have, and will have processes of origin, development and transformation, the hard core of this theory are *the ethnic processes*; that is, the evolutionary and/or transformative changes that take place in the historical course of the peoples. Three factors must be considered: *intra-ethnic factors*, which depend on the development of each ethnic group in its historical process; *inter-ethnic factors*, depending on the relations of coexistence and neighborliness with other peoples; and *extra-ethnic factors*, which are due to the ecological-natural characteristics of the environment and other social and economic factors (ecological changes, natural disasters, wars, etc.).¹⁹

The above makes it possible to characterize ethnic processes as evolutionary, transforming and evolutionary/transforming, as follows:

1. In evolutionary ethnic processes, the ethnos remains stable, and two types are appreciated: *intra-ethnic consolidation*, which manifests itself through the internal cohesion of the different ethnic traits and their peculiarities; and *inter-ethnic integration*, through the emergence of a certain cultural community that preserves its ethnic traits, as in the case of the Swiss.
2. In transformative ethnic processes, ethnos changes qualitatively and three types are appreciated: *ethnogenetic division*, separation of one or more parts of the main ethnos and formation of one or more new peoples with their own characteristics; this can be seen, for example, in the transatlantic slave trade of enslaved Africans and in the formation of new peoples in the Americas and the Caribbean;²⁰ *ethnogenetic consolidation*, by the fusion of several ethnic units related in their linguistic-cultural traits into a larger ethnic unit; and *ethnogenetic mixing*, by the fusion of several ethnic units without kinship ties or related cultural traits, as in the case of Cuba, with respect to its

¹⁸ See, Pedro Ceinos (coord.). *Minorías étnicas. La guía más completa y actual sobre la situación de los pueblos indígenas en los cinco continentes*. Barcelona, 1990.

¹⁹ See Yulián Bromlei. «Procesos étnicos: característica general», in *Op. Cit.*: 106-121.

²⁰ See Darcy Riveiro. «Las Américas y la civilización», in *El proceso civilizatorio*, Havana, 1992:215-263.

aboriginal, European, African, Asian, insular Caribbean and other components.²¹

3. In the evolutionary/transforming ethnic processes, the assimilating ethnos evolves, since it incorporates new traits as part of its consolidation, and the assimilated ethnos transforms, since it loses its previous ethnic traits. This is the process of *ethnic assimilation*, which consists of the dissolution of small groups or isolated representatives of an ethnos into a larger one. This type of assimilation can be *natural* through prolonged peaceful coexistence, along with various mixed marriages; and *forced* when policies of ethnocide and other subtle or violent forms of assimilation are applied: mass sterilization, induced migration and others related to the absence of civil and cultural rights.²²

Gómez's misguided critique of ethnic/ethnicity also gives him cause to lash out against the notion of *memory*, another highly topical issue where neoliberal political discourse tries to impose historical amnesia and only value "the here and now" as the main existential resource.²³ Another totally contrary approach has been promoted by UNESCO through the International Slave Route Project: Resistance, Freedom and Heritage to reconcile history and memory, as part of a constant presence of Africa's legacy worldwide.²⁴

Thus, Gómez's supposed "academic language" is subordinated to the ideology of de-ideologization to promote oblivion. In this sense he considers:

A synonym of identity consciousness is constituted by "memory", which is what remains after taking stock of forgetting. It would be necessary to debate the nature of this memory and the entity of its subject. All memory is reproducible and transmissible without restriction, insofar as it is culturally codified. But, by presenting it as the "historical memory of a people", the fact that at the same time it is or can be the memory of humanity and that

²¹ See Jesús Guancho. *Componentes étnicos de la nación cubana*, (third edition) Havana, 2011.

²² See Jesús Guancho. «¿Son los pueblos entidades inalterables?», in *1000 preguntas/respuestas*, Editorial Félix Varela, vol. 4, Havana, 2014:829.

²³ A resource that is contrary to the human condition, since memory is a function of the brain and a process of the mind that allows the organism to encode, store and retrieve information from the past. Thus, to override memory is a pathological inducement.

²⁴ See Matthieu Dussauge (Direction). *La route de l'esclave. Des itinéraires pour réconcilier histoire et mémoire*. Le Conseil Départemental de la Guadeloupe, L'Harmattan, 2016; Nelly Schmidt (Coord). *Legacies of Slavery: A Handbook for Managers of Sites and Itineraries of Memory*, (in English and French), UNESCO, Paris, 2017; URL: <http://www.unesco.org/new/en/social-and-human-sciences/themes/slave-route/right-box/publications/legacies-of-slavery/> and Ali Moussa Iye, Nelly Schmidt y Paul E. Lovejoy (Eds). *Slavery, Resistance and Abolitions. A Pluralist Perspective*. Africa World Press, 2020.

there are no chromosomal or cerebral objections for any human being to appropriate this memory as his own is being concealed.

After alluding to some examples of worldwide scope such as the Arabic numerals, the foods and condiments domesticated in Africa, Asia or America, the horrors of the Inquisition, the Nazi holocaust, Hiroshima, the Gulag, the monstrosity of atomic fission, the beauty of all the arts, the varieties of culinary taste, the advances of science, Internet..., he considers that:

The memory of the ancestors is not that of the imaginary ancestors of "my people", but in fact that of the ancestors of all. What myopia to defend that "memory" links us to "our grandparents" and to "our grandchildren", as if cultural inheritances do not pass from one individual to another without any kinship between them. There is no biogenetic link on which this memory necessarily depends. The subject "people" is a concept that appears as weak as that of ethnicity. Populations do not present a closed continuity in their biological inheritance and much less in their cultural transmission.

It is a real contribution, certainly very conscious, to erase the memory of individuals and groups as a resource of human subjectivity, as much of the patrimonial goods as of the senses of belonging and their roles. After this disquisition it would be necessary to see who should go to the oculist, either for myopia or blindness. In the individual and collective memory not only remains what provides a sense of belonging to a certain human group, but also the accumulated knowledge about local and global atrocities to ensure that these experiences are not repeated and that, although they are part of the past, they are not forgotten. In this sense, the construction of a counter-hegemonic discourse from the scientific activity lies in subjecting to criticism those who lend themselves in a direct, mimetic, or complacent way to follow the game of world domination through the annulment of identities as a means of crushing the diversity of cultural expressions.

Still dissatisfied with his tropes, he tackles "The Ethnic Mirage" to bring his views to a close. To be consistent with his inconsistency he points out that:

The "markers of ethnicity", the "signs of identity", cover only a handful of real or imaginary differences, which may not always be false, but whose partiality is patent with respect to the socio-historical whole, from which they are limited to extract and interpret only a few traits. Most of the time they involve an arbitrary choice of minimal traits, useful for a certain contrast with others: barely a wrapper or label with respect to the total system of constituent characters. Here the part does not represent the whole,

but masks it. By pointing out fragmentary and variable components, it is not understood wherein the ethnic resides.

The fact that the author does not understand it and therefore does not interpret it adequately, does not imply that the features are false or imagined, both in the field of subjectivity and objective evidence. The current social movements in Latin America, for example, that unite and have their own voice in favor of their human, social and cultural rights, are very well marked by their sense of belonging/difference, not only to their respective nations, but to the peoples (ethnos) of which they are part, many of them inter-border, such as the Amazon, whose extension reaches 6 million km² that includes eight countries, of which Brazil and Peru have the largest extension, together with Bolivia, Colombia, Ecuador, Guyana, Venezuela and Surinam. In this part of the world, hundreds of aboriginal peoples play a fundamental role in the adaptation to this great lung of the Earth, but they also represent a critical conscience in the face of deforestation and the lack of joint actions of the respective countries, aimed at the rational use of natural resources, particularly water.

Notwithstanding this evidence from the other side of Europe, Gómez emphasizes that: "The presumed "ethnic category" (the common traits that form its "collective representation", with a historical background) may reflect only an illusion, or else simply cover other distinct categories: for example, a category of *caste* (in India), or of *social class* (the poor peasants), or of religious *confession* (the Orthodox Jews)". All these specific categories, in the social or confessional structure, are part of the complexity of ethnos at the global level, hence their richness and wide variability. The issue lies precisely in studying their regularities and assessing how they evolve and transform in time-space. It is something like the principle of water, because of its liquid condition, it always adapts to the container that holds it, from a thimble to an ocean. If this author has already drowned in the thimble, let alone what would happen to him in the ocean.

He culminates his text with another idea more unhappy than the previous ones: "Ethnicity", like "race", only acquire social existence when they are used for political discrimination". Once again, the virus of Eurocentrism contaminates and sickens him. Nothing could be further from the realities of America and the Caribbean. A very representative part of the American people identified as African American, highly racialized by the system and convinced of their cause, commonly use the notion of "race" to defend their civil rights against exclusions in their own country. On the other hand, many social movements of aboriginal lineage in Latin America use the notion of ethnicity precisely to combat political

discrimination in a historical-cultural, territorial, linguistic and identity sense and not in its already limited biological scope.

In view of the above, it is of great interest to evaluate the discourse that annuls identities to confirm that when it comes to globalizing a single way of thinking, identities get in the way. It is also a way of invalidating the role of cultural diversity as a component of the human species.

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